

MISMATCH BETWEEN ABM STRAND AND HIGHER EDUCATION COURSES: ADDRESSING THE GAP THROUGH ENHANCED CAREER PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the extent of alignment and mismatch between the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand completed by graduates of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School in School Year 2023–2024 and the higher education courses they pursued in Academic Year 2024–2025. Utilizing a descriptive research design and total enumeration sampling, data were gathered from 193 traceable graduates using a validated online survey instrument administered through Google Forms. Quantitative data, including graduation rates, curriculum exits, and vertical articulation of college programs, were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, and measures of central tendency, while qualitative responses were examined through thematic analysis to identify factors contributing to mismatch and strategies for prevention. Results indicate that 88.60% of graduates pursued higher education, with 91.81% enrolling in vertically articulated courses such as Accounting, Business Administration, and Marketing Management, reflecting strong strand–course alignment. However, 8.19% pursued non-aligned programs due to financial constraints, limited availability of desired courses, decision-making challenges, shifting interests, and perceived better employment opportunities outside the ABM field. The findings underscore the need for strengthened institutional interventions, including enhanced career guidance, greater exposure to academic pathways, and increased parental involvement. The study proposes the development of an improved career guidance program—“Oplan DECIDE”—to support informed and future-oriented course selection among senior high school learners.

Keywords: *ABM Strand, career guidance, course mismatch, Higher Education, Oplan DECIDE*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a critical role in shaping learners' future opportunities, influencing their perspectives, competencies, and long-term career pathways. As emphasized by international and local educational frameworks, quality education equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to participate meaningfully in society and thrive in rapidly changing environments (The World Bank, n.d.; Geneva College, 2020). In the Philippines, the implementation of the K–12 curriculum through the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 sought to strengthen this preparation by introducing specialized senior high school (SHS) tracks and strands aligned with students' intended higher education or career goals (DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012). Within this structure, the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand is specifically designed to prepare learners for business-related programs in college and future professional endeavors.

Despite this intention, research has shown persistent issues of strand–course misalignment among SHS graduates nationwide. Course mismatch occurs when students pursue higher education programs that do not correspond with their SHS specialization, often affecting their academic performance, motivation, and career readiness (Quintos et al., 2020). Studies reveal that some ABM students choose the strand based on external influences—such as family expectations or limited understanding of its implications—rather than informed interest, resulting in difficulties when transitioning to college-level business courses (De Guzman & Mercado, 2019). Other research identifies gaps in students' preparedness for specialized subjects, noting challenges in higher-level mathematics, accounting, and managerial concepts despite their ABM background (Rodriguez & Tan, 2020). Moreover, insufficient career guidance and limited exposure to pathways have been found to contribute to uninformed decisions that ultimately lead to strand–course mismatch (Navarro & Peralta, 2019; Santos & Villar, 2018).

While existing literature acknowledges the prevalence of mismatch and identifies its causes, there remains a research gap in understanding the specific patterns and factors influencing ABM graduates at the local school level, particularly in emerging cities like Carmona, Cavite. With higher education enrollment trends continuing to evolve and students facing increasing pressure to make career-defining decisions, examining these issues at the grassroots level becomes timely and essential. The present study responds to this gap by determining the extent of alignment between the ABM strand and the higher education courses pursued by graduates of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School (ALLSHS) for School Year 2023–2024. Furthermore, it explores the underlying reasons for potential mismatches and assesses the adequacy of existing career guidance initiatives.

By identifying the factors that influence students' educational pathways, the study aims to provide evidence-based insights necessary for strengthening institutional support mechanisms. In particular, the study proposes the enhancement of the school's Career Guidance Program through an intervention titled "Oplan DECIDE," designed to help learners make informed, realistic, and well-aligned academic and career decisions. This research is therefore significant not only in addressing an emerging local concern but also in contributing to broader efforts to reduce strand–course mismatch and improve student transition outcomes within the Philippine education system.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the possible mismatch between the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand completed by graduates of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for School Year 2023–2024 and the higher education courses they pursued in Academic Year 2024–2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the graduation rate of ABM students from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for School Year 2023–2024, and how many graduates pursued the various curriculum exits such as higher education, mid-level skills development, entrepreneurship, and employment?
2. What percentage of graduates enrolled in higher education programs that are vertically articulated and not vertically articulated with the ABM strand?
3. What factors influence ABM graduates' decisions when choosing their higher education courses, and what reasons contribute to potential strand–course mismatch?
4. How can senior high school students avoid the possibility of mismatch between the ABM strand and their chosen college program?
5. How can the Career Guidance Program of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School be enhanced to serve as an effective tool in preventing mismatch between the ABM strand and higher education courses?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in a public senior high school located in Carmona City, Cavite. The locale offers the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand under the K–12 curriculum, with graduates proceeding to various higher education institutions nationwide. The specific name of the school is withheld in adherence to publication and confidentiality requirements.

Research Design

A descriptive research design was employed to examine the extent of strand–course alignment among ABM graduates and identify factors contributing to possible mismatch between their senior high school specialization and chosen higher education programs. This design allowed the researchers to describe prevailing patterns, behaviors, and decisions relevant to the students' educational trajectories.

Respondents and Sampling Method

The study utilized total enumeration sampling, targeting all 227 ABM graduates from School Year 2023–2024. This approach ensured the inclusion of the entire accessible population. Of the total graduates, 193 respondents provided complete survey responses, representing an 85.02% response rate, while the remaining 34 were untraceable at the time of data collection. Respondents included graduates who were enrolled full-time in any higher education institution during Academic Year 2024–2025, while those not enrolled in college or untraceable were excluded.

Research Instrument

Data were gathered using a researcher-made survey questionnaire administered electronically via Google Forms. The instrument consisted of sections capturing:

- (a) demographic information,
- (b) curriculum exit and chosen higher education program, and
- (c) factors influencing course decisions.

The questionnaire contained both quantitative items—including multiple-choice and checklist-type questions—and qualitative open-ended items designed to explore students' decision-making experiences. Prior to full administration, the instrument underwent pilot testing and re-testing to ensure clarity, reliability, and internal validity. Expert validation was conducted to review item construction, alignment with research objectives, and ethical compliance. Necessary revisions were incorporated before final deployment.

Data Gathering Procedure

Approval of conducting the study was obtained from relevant school authorities. The researchers coordinated with former class advisers for the dissemination of survey links and informed consent forms. Respondents aged 18 and above indicated their voluntary participation by selecting “Yes” in the consent portion of the Google Form. Confidentiality, anonymity, and data privacy were strictly observed throughout the process. Data collection was conducted from November to December 2024.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using:

Frequency counts and percentages to determine graduation rates, curriculum exits, and the degree of vertical articulation between the ABM strand and college courses; and

Measures of central tendency to describe general patterns in the distribution of responses.

Qualitative responses regarding factors leading to mismatch, ways to avoid mismatch, and improvements to career guidance services were analyzed using thematic analysis. This process involved coding responses, identifying recurring concepts, and generating themes that represent participants' perspectives.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused exclusively on the alignment between the ABM strand and the higher education programs pursued by graduates from one public senior high school. It did not include other SHS strands or schools, limiting the generalizability of results. Only graduates enrolled in higher education institutions were included, as the study specifically investigated strand–course articulation. Self-reported survey responses may also be subject to recall bias or subjective interpretation. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into ABM students' post-SHS educational pathways and factors affecting course selection.

RESULTS

Table 1. Graduation Rate and Post-Graduation Pathways of ABM Strand Graduates at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, SY 2023-2024

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Target Respondents (Response Rate)	193	85.02%
Untraceable Respondents	34	14.98%
Total ABM Graduates (Graduation Rate)	227	100.00 %

Table 1 presents the data for the graduates of the ABM (Accountancy, Business, and Management) strand at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for the School Year 2023-2024. The school achieved a 100% graduation rate, with 227 students successfully completing the program. Out of the total graduates, 193 respondents (85.02%) provided information about their post-graduation pathways, while 34 respondents (14.98%) were untraceable. The respondents pursued various curriculum exits, including higher education, mid-level skills development, entrepreneurship, and employment. This distribution reflects the diverse career and education choices made by the graduates of the ABM strand.

Table 2. Distribution of ABM Strand Graduates' Post-Graduation Paths for School Year 2023-2024

<i>Course/Program</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rate</i>
Bachelor of Science in Accounting	51	29.82
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	14	8.19
Bachelor of Science in Real Estate Management	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Human Resource Management	15	8.77
Bachelor of Science in Marketing Management	29	16.96
Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship	4	2.34
Bachelor of Science in Financial Management	2	1.17
Bachelor of Science in Economics	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Public Administration	0	0.00
Bachelor of Science in Accounting Information Systems	0	0.00
Bachelor of Science in Commerce	0	0.00
Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	16	9.36
Bachelor of Science in Managerial Accounting	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	22	12.87
Others	14	8.19
Subtotal	171	88.60
Employment	15	7.77
Entrepreneurship	5	2.59
Mid-level Skills Development	2	1.04
Total	193	100.0

Table 2 shows the graduates for the School Year 2023-2024, Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School's ABM (Accountancy, Business, and Management) strand, it has a graduation percentage of 88.60%, with 171 graduates in various ABM programs. These courses include Bachelor of Science in Accounting, Business Administration, Marketing Management, and Tourism Management, among others.

In terms of professional pathways and additional education, 15 graduates (7.77%) found work, 5 (2.59%) started their own businesses, and 2 (1.04%) focused on mid-level skill development. The remaining graduates (171) pursued higher study.

Figure 1. Frequency Rate of Curriculum Exits of Graduated ABM Students

Table 3. Distribution of ABM Strand Graduates' Enrollment in Vertically and Non-Vertically Articulated Higher Education Courses for School Year 2023-2024

Vertically Articulated	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor of Science in Accounting	51	29.82
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	14	8.19
Bachelor of Science in Real Estate Management	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Human Resource Management	15	8.77
Bachelor of Science in Marketing Management	29	16.96
Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship	4	2.34
Bachelor of Science in Financial Management	2	1.17
Bachelor of Science in Economics	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Public Administration	0	0.00
Bachelor of Science in Accounting Information Systems	0	0.00
Bachelor of Science in Commerce	0	0.00

Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	16	9.36
Bachelor of Science in Managerial Accounting	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	22	12.87
Subtotal	157	91.81
Not Vertically Articulated	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	2	1.17
Bachelor of Science in Architecture	2	1.17
Bachelor of Science in Aviation Aircraft Maintenance	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Education	3	1.75
Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	1	0.58
Computer System Servicing NC II	1	0.58
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	2	1.17
Civil Engineering	1	0.58
Subtotal	14	8.19
Total	171	100

Table 3 depicts the distribution of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School's (ALLSHS) ABM strand graduates who went on to study higher education courses, demonstrating the congruence of their chosen professions with the ABM curriculum. A large 91.81% (157) of graduates chose courses that are vertically aligned with the ABM strand, such as degrees in Accounting, Business Administration, Marketing Management, and Tourism Management. This suggests a good connection with the ABM track, which represents a straight continuation of their senior high school study. In contrast, 8.19% (14 graduates) chose disciplines not vertically aligned with ABM, such as nursing, architecture, and education. While these selections stray from the ABM focus, they reflect the graduates' various professional interests. Understanding the elements that influence these decisions, including personal aspirations or external influences, could provide insights into future educational pathways for ABM students.

Figure 2. Frequency Rate of Vertically Articulated Courses of Graduated ABM Students

Figure 3: Frequency Rate of Non-Vertically Articulated Courses of Graduated ABM Students

THEME 1. EDUCATIONAL AVAILABILITY OF COURSES

This issue covers the restricted availability of Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) courses at various institutions. Many participants were frustrated by the lack of alternatives that matched their academic background, forcing them to make concessions in their course decisions. One participant stated, "The program I wanted was not offered

at my university." Ramos et al. (2023) found comparable results, demonstrating that a shortage of appropriate programs might considerably affect students' educational paths and contribute to course mismatch. Because of the limited course selections, students are sometimes forced to enroll in programs that do not match their interests or past studies.

THEME 2. FINANCIAL CONSTRAINT

When it came to choosing higher education courses, participants typically identified financial constraints as a significant hindrance. Many students are discouraged from obtaining ABM degrees because of the exorbitant prices involved. A participant stated, "I had to choose a less expensive program because I couldn't afford my first choice." According to Mendoza's (2022) study, financial constraints are a common issue among students in the Philippines, with many unable to pursue their desired fields due to tuition fees and other costs. This financial strain sometimes causes a mismatch between students' interests and their selected courses.

THEME 3. DECISION-MAKING CHALLENGES

The subject of decision-making issues represents the uncertainty that students endure in their senior year of high school. Many participants acknowledged feeling rushed and confused while selecting their strands, which influenced their college selections. One participant stated, "I didn't really know what I wanted back then." Research by Santos et al. (2024) underlines the significance of informed decision-making in educational routes, pointing out that early hesitation might lead to misalignment between high school and college courses. This ambiguity might lead to students enrolling in programs that do not align with their initial academic interests.

THEME 4. SHIFT OF INTEREST

A noticeable pattern among participants was a shift of interest from their original ABM-related goals to other subjects once they entered college. This shift was frequently driven by fresh passions or realizations about personal strengths. One participant commented, "I initially wanted to study business but found my passion in psychology instead." Lim et al.'s (2023) research confirms this finding, demonstrating that students commonly reevaluate their career aspirations when they receive exposure to new subjects and experiences. Such developments can result in major mismatches between high school strands and college courses.

THEME 5. PERCEIVED BETTER OPPORTUNITIES

Many participants believed that non-ABM disciplines provided greater career chances and employment security; hence, they chose alternative courses. One participant stated, "I felt Nursing would provide more job security than Business." Research by Cruz et al. (2023) discovered that students are more driven to sectors perceived to have higher employment rates and earnings, moving them away from conventional ABM pathways. This emphasis on pragmatism over passion can lead to course incompatibilities because students prioritize perceived economic benefits over alignment with past schooling.

THEME 6. ENHANCED CAREER GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING

This subject underline the significance of good career advising and counselling services in senior high schools. By giving students access to expert counselors, they may obtain individualized assistance on how to link their ABM strand with relevant college courses. One participant stated, "Having a counselor who understands my interests helped me choose the right course." Research shows that when students engage in comprehensive career planning, they are more likely to choose courses that reflect their strengths and aspirations, reducing the likelihood of mismatch.

According to research by Reyes et al. (2024), students who participated in formal career counseling programs were considerably less likely to encounter course mismatch than those who did not. The study emphasizes the importance of making educated decisions in schooling pathways, suggesting that proactive guidance can lead to better alignment between high school strands and college courses.

THEME 7. EXPOSURE TO DIVERSE CAREER OPTIONS

This topic highlights the need for a curriculum that is closely aligned with accessible college programs. Many students reported a lack of understanding of which college courses related with their ABM strand, resulting in poor selections. One participant commented, "I didn't know what courses matched my strand until it was too late." Increasing curriculum clarity and giving materials about various college tracks will help students make more informed decisions.

Formaran et al. (2022) found that connecting senior high school courses with college programs might dramatically reduce mismatch rates. The study stresses that when students understand the educational pathway from their strand to future college courses, they are more likely to follow options that correspond to their previous knowledge.

THEME 8. PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND SUPPORT

This subject examines the role of parental engagement in students' educational decisions. Many participants said that having supportive parents who pushed them to pursue their interests helped them make better decisions about their college courses. According to one participant, "My parents helped me research what I could do with my ABM background."

Batu et al. (2018) discovered that family support is critical in steering kids to appropriate educational routes. According to the research, when parents actively participate in their children's decision-making processes, teenagers are less likely to discover incompatibilities between their high school strands and college courses.

These themes highlight the significance of advice, knowledge, exposure, and assistance as critical ways for senior high school students to prevent mismatches between their ABM strand and future college courses.

THEME 9. COMPREHENSIVE CAREER COUNSELING

To effectively prevent mismatches between the ABM strand and college courses, the career guidance program at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School should prioritize comprehensive career counseling. This includes providing students with personalized sessions where they can explore their interests, strengths, and potential career paths. A participant noted, "Having one-on-one sessions with a counselor helped me understand my options better."

Research indicates that personalized career counseling significantly enhances students' decision-making processes regarding their educational and career paths. According to a study by Mathur and Mishra (2024), effective career guidance programs that incorporate individual assessments can lead to more informed choices among students, thereby reducing the likelihood of course mismatch.

THEME 10: INTEGRATION OF CAREER EDUCATION IN CURRICULUM

Integrating career education into the existing curriculum is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of the career guidance program. By embedding career-related discussions and activities within regular lessons, students can better understand how their current studies relate to future careers. One educator mentioned, "When we connect classroom learning to real-world applications, students become more engaged and informed about their choices."

A study by Kuder (2018) emphasizes the importance of connecting academic content with career skills, suggesting that this approach not only prepares students for their future careers but also fosters a culture of continuous learning and adaptability. This integration can help students see the relevance of their ABM strand in various college courses.

THEME 11. EXPOSURE TO DIVERSE CAREER PATHWAYS

Providing students with exposure to a variety of career pathways is essential for broadening their perspectives on potential college courses. This can be achieved through workshops, guest speakers from various industries, and field trips to businesses related to the ABM strand. A participant shared, "Learning about different careers from professionals opened my eyes to options I hadn't considered before."

Research by Batu et al. (2018) supports this notion, indicating that exposure to diverse career options helps students make more informed decisions about their educational paths. The study highlights that when students are aware of multiple pathways, they are less likely to choose courses that do not align with their backgrounds.

THEME 12. PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN CAREER GUIDANCE

Enhancing parental involvement in the career guidance process can significantly impact students' decision-making regarding their college courses. Organizing workshops for

parents about available educational pathways and how they can support their children's choices can create a more supportive environment for students. One parent noted, "Understanding what my child is interested in helped me guide them better."

A study by Formaran et al. (2022) found that parental support plays a critical role in reducing course mismatches among students. The research indicates that when parents are informed and involved in the decision-making process, students are more likely to pursue courses aligned with their academic backgrounds.

THEME 13. CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR COUNSELORS

To ensure the effectiveness of the career guidance program, continuous professional development for school counselors is vital. Training on current labor market trends, emerging careers, and effective counseling techniques will equip counselors with the necessary skills to guide students effectively. A counselor remarked, "Staying updated on industry trends allows me to provide relevant advice to my students."

Research indicates that well-trained counselors are better equipped to facilitate meaningful discussions about career choices with students. According to findings from Moya (2018), ongoing professional development enhances counselors' ability to support student decision-making processes effectively.

DISCUSSION

Graduation Rate and Post-Graduation Pathways

The results show that all 227 ABM students successfully completed their senior high school program, representing a 100% graduation rate. Of these graduates, 193 (85.02%) were traceable and participated in the study, while 34 (14.98%) were untraceable. Among the respondents, the majority (88.60%) pursued higher education, whereas smaller proportions entered employment (7.77%), entrepreneurship (2.59%), or mid-level skills development (1.04%).

These trends demonstrate that ABM graduates predominantly view higher education as their primary curriculum exit. This is consistent with the intention of the K–12 curriculum to equip learners with academic foundations for tertiary studies (DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012). Rodriguez and Tan (2020) similarly found that ABM graduates commonly continue to business-related college programs due to the strand's academic orientation. The low percentages of employment and entrepreneurship mirror the findings of Navarro and Peralta (2019), who noted that many SHS learners perceive college as essential for long-term employability and career advancement. Meanwhile, the small number entering the workforce supports Mendoza's (2022) claim that financial considerations sometimes push students to work immediately after SHS, though this trend remained minimal in the present study.

Distribution of Higher Education Programs Pursued

Of the 171 ABM graduates who enrolled in higher education institutions, most pursued business-related programs, including BS Accounting (29.82%), BS Marketing Management (16.96%), BS Human Resource Management (8.77%), BS Tourism Management (12.87%), and other ABM-aligned courses. The small proportion (8.19%) who enrolled in unrelated programs, such as Nursing, Education, and Information Technology, reflects a minority of students whose course choices diverged from their SHS specialization.

The strong preference for ABM-related college courses reinforces De Guzman and Mercado's (2019) findings that many students choose strands and degrees based on perceived alignment and preparation. Santos and Villar (2018) also reported that SHS strands generally influence college course selection, though personal interest and external influences—such as parents and peers—may lead some students to pursue unrelated fields. Thus, while the majority of graduates maintained vertical alignment, the presence of mismatches supports earlier studies documenting the complex interplay of interest, influence, and opportunity in course selection (Quintos et al., 2020).

Vertical and Non-Vertical Articulation of College Courses

Analysis of vertical articulation indicates that 157 graduates (91.81%) enrolled in programs directly aligned with the ABM strand, while 14 students (8.19%) pursued courses not vertically articulated with ABM. This demonstrates a high degree of strand–course alignment, affirming the effectiveness of the ABM curriculum in preparing students for business programs in higher education.

The findings are consistent with Rodriguez and Tan (2020), who observed that ABM learners generally feel prepared for and interested in business-related academic tracks. At the same time, the identified mismatch resonates with the work of Quintos et al. (2020) and Diaz and Mendoza (2021), who noted that mismatches persist due to decision-making challenges, lack of guidance, or changes in career interests. The presence of a mismatch—though small—signals a continuing need for strengthened support systems to ensure informed course selection.

Factors Influencing Course Selection and Contributors to Mismatch

Qualitative analysis revealed five prominent factors shaping students' course choices:

1. Limited availability of desired courses,
2. Financial constraints,
3. Decision-making difficulties,
4. Shift in personal interests, and
5. Perceived better employment opportunities in non-ABM fields.

Limited availability of programs echoes Ramos et al. (2023), who identified institutional offerings as a major constraint affecting course choices. Financial challenges align with

Mendoza's (2022) findings that economic pressures significantly shape educational decisions. Decision-making difficulties support Santos and Villar (2018), who emphasized that many students lack complete understanding of strand–course alignment during SHS selection. Shifting interests are consistent with Lim et al. (2023), who reported that exposure to new academic contexts often leads students to re-evaluate their aspirations. Finally, choosing courses based on perceived labor market demand aligns with Cruz et al. (2023), who found that students often prioritize employability over initial interests or strand alignment.

Overall, these results are highly consistent with the literature, affirming that both personal and external factors contribute to strand–course mismatch.

Strategies for Preventing Strand–Course Mismatch

Graduates suggested several mechanisms for reducing mismatch, including:

- Enhanced and continuous career guidance,
- Greater exposure to career options,
- Increased parental involvement.

These strategies align with Reyes et al. (2024), who demonstrated that structured career counseling significantly reduces mismatches. They also echo Formaran et al. (2022), who emphasized the importance of connecting SHS learning experiences to actual academic pathways. Likewise, Batu et al. (2018) found that parental support and involvement positively influence aligned course decision-making.

Thus, the students' proposed strategies are consistent with previous research, reinforcing the need for robust support mechanisms within schools.

Enhancing the Career Guidance Program

Themes emerging from participant responses emphasized the need to strengthen the school's Career Guidance Program (CGP) through:

- Comprehensive, individualized career counseling;
- Curriculum-embedded career education;
- Increased exposure to industry pathways;
- Parental involvement;
- Continuous professional development for counselors.

These recommendations align with Mathur and Mishra (2024), who emphasized the impact of structured guidance programs on informed career decisions. Kuder (2018) likewise highlighted the value of embedding career education into subject instruction, while Moya (2018) stressed the need for ongoing counselor training to ensure updated labor-market knowledge.

The proposed “Oplan DECIDE” reflects these recommendations and offers a targeted intervention aimed at reducing mismatch through informed decision-making, aligning both with the literature and the identified needs within the school context.

Across all quantitative and qualitative results, the study reveals a predominantly aligned strand–course progression among ABM graduates, accompanied by a small but meaningful presence of mismatch. The results consistently support the related literature’s findings that while SHS strands effectively prepare students for aligned pathways, personal, institutional, and socioeconomic factors continue to shape students’ decisions. These findings underscore the importance of a strengthened Career Guidance Program to ensure that learners make accurate, well-informed, and future-oriented career decisions.

Conclusions

To accomplish the objectives of the study, this chapter presents, illustrates, and explains the conclusions drawn from the information gathered. The following results are what the researchers concluded in the study:

1. According to the study's findings, the vast majority of ABM graduates from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School (ALLSHS) for the School Year 2023-2024 (88.60%) chose further education courses related to their academic background in Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM). This alignment represents a favorable trend in which students further their education in subjects that are relevant to their senior high school strand. However, a lower proportion (8.19%) chose non-vertically articulated courses, demonstrating the graduates' broad professional goals and interests. While most students remained on track, the decision to take courses outside of the ABM strand reflects personal interests or anticipated greater employment chances in other sectors.
2. The study of the factors that influence ABM graduates' course choices emphasizes the significance of personal interests, financial restrictions, and job possibilities. Many students chose degrees in high-demand sectors like healthcare or engineering because they believed they would provide more career stability and financial benefits. Furthermore, financial constraints had a significant influence, as many students were forced to select more cheap choices, resulting in a mismatch between their ABM strand and chosen college courses. Other variables, such as a shift in personal interests or a lack of educated decision-making in senior high school, also contributed to the mismatch. It is clear that personal and external circumstances have a considerable impact on the pathways that ABM students choose after graduation.
3. The study underlines the need of improving career advising and counseling in minimizing incompatibilities between the ABM strand and higher education courses. It implies that a comprehensive career counseling program that includes tailored sessions and career education in the curriculum might help students make

better judgments. Exposure to a variety of professional trajectories, as well as parental participation, are important components of this process since they extend pupils' awareness of various job alternatives. Schools that incorporate career advising throughout the educational process might help students better connect their academic interests with their selected higher education courses, lowering the chance of course mismatch.

4. To further improve the efficacy of ALLSHS's career advising program, counselors must receive ongoing professional development to ensure they are updated on labor market trends and developing employment opportunities. Integrating career education into the normal curriculum would enable students to link their studies to real-world applications, allowing them to make more informed decisions about their future. Furthermore, increasing parental engagement in decision-making would provide a more supportive atmosphere for kids, improving their capacity to make the best career decisions.
5. The study indicates that, while the majority of ABM graduates continue education that is consistent with their academic path, the occurrence of mismatches owing to financial restrictions, changing professional interests, and a lack of informed decision-making need focused assistance. Schools may better prepare students to make well-informed, conscientious decisions about their post-graduation paths by enhancing career counseling programs, providing clearer exposure to different career paths, and actively involve parents in the decision-making process.

Recommendations

The researchers suggest that more collaborations between Senior High Schools (SHS), Higher Education Institutions, companies, and the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) can greatly enhance the practical learning experience for students, better equip them for the workforce, and ensure that the educational system aligns with industry needs. The researchers recommend changing the respondents with different tracks and strands to be able to find the perceptions of other students as they can also experience this kind of situation. Since the study used Google Forms in collecting the data, the researchers recommend using interviews or focus group discussions as these are some of the most effective ways of collecting data.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that this study complied with all ethical standards for research involving human participants. Informed consent was obtained, and respondents were free to withdraw at any time. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained in accordance with Data Privacy guidelines, and participants' well-being was safeguarded throughout the study. The authors affirm that no conflict of interest exists, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all findings were interpreted objectively and without bias. The results were used solely for research purposes. For transparency, the authors disclose that AI

(ChatGPT) was used only for language refinement; all analyses and conclusions remain the authors' own work.

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